

Delphine Larivière^{1,*}, Linelle Abueg^{2,*}, Nadolina Brajuka^{2,*}, Cristóbal Gallardo-Alba³, Bjorn Grüning³, Byung June Ko⁴, Alex Ostrovsky⁵, Marc Palmada-Flores⁶, Brandon D. Pickett⁷, Keon Rabbani⁸, Agostinho Antunes^{9,10}, Jennifer R. Balacco², Mark JP Chaisson⁸, Haoyu Cheng^{11,12}, Joanna Collins¹³, Melanie Couture², Alexandra Denisova¹⁴, Olivier Fedrigo², Guido Roberto Gallo¹⁵, Alice Maria Giani¹⁶, Grenville MacDonald Gooder², Kathleen Horan², Nivesh Jain², Cassidy Johnson², Heebal Kim^{4,17,18}, Chul Lee^{18,19}, Tomas Marques-Bonet^{6,20,21,22}, Brian O'Toole², Arang Rhie⁷, Simona Secomandi²³, Marcella Sozzoni²⁴, Tatiana Tilley², Marcela Uliano-Silva²⁵, Marius van den Beek¹, Robert W. Williams²⁶, Robert M. Waterhouse²⁷, Adam M. Phillippy⁷, Erich D. Jarvis^{2,†}, Michael C. Schatz^{5,†}, Anton Nekrutenko^{1,†}, Giulio Formenti^{2,†}

* Co-First author

† Co-Corresponding author

¹ Dept. of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16801, USA

² Vertebrate Genome Laboratory, The Rockefeller University, NY 10065, USA

³ Bioinformatics Group, Department of Computer Science, Albert-Ludwigs-University Freiburg, 79098 Freiburg, Germany

⁴ Department of Agricultural Biotechnology and Research Institute of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Seoul National University, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea

⁵ Departments of Biology and Computer Science, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore MD 21218, USA

⁶ Department of Medicine and Life Sciences (MELIS), Institut de Biologia Evolutiva, Universitat Pompeu Fabra-CSIC, Barcelona 08003, Spain

⁷ Genome Informatics Section, Computational and Statistical Genomics Branch, National Human Genome Research Institute, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD 20892, USA

⁸ Department of Quantitative and Computational Biology, University of Southern California, CA 90089, USA

⁹ CIIMAR/CIMAR, Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research, University of Porto, 4450-208 Porto, Portugal

¹⁰ Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, 4169-007, Porto, Portugal

¹¹ Department of Data Sciences, Dana-Farber Cancer Institute, Boston, MA 02215, USA

¹² Department of Biomedical Informatics, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA 02115, USA

¹³ Wellcome Sanger Institute, Cambridge CB10 1SA, United Kingdom

¹⁴ Faculty of Bioengineering and Bioinformatics, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow 119991 Russia

¹⁵ Department of Biosciences, University of Milan, 20126 Milan, Italy

¹⁶ BMRI, Weill Cornell Medical College, New York City, NY 10065 USA

¹⁷ eGnome, Inc, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea

¹⁸ Interdisciplinary Program in Bioinformatics, Seoul National University, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea

¹⁹ Laboratory of Neurogenetics of Language, The Rockefeller University, New York City, NY, 10065, USA

²⁰ Catalan Institution of Research and Advanced Studies (ICREA), Barcelona 08010, Spain

²¹ CNAG, Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG), Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology (BIST), Barcelona 08028, Spain

²² Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Cerdanyola del Vallès 08193, Spain

²³ Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cyprus, 2200 Nicosia, Cyprus

²⁴ University of Florence, Department of Biology, Via Madonna del Piano 6, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino (FI)

²⁵ Tree of Life, Wellcome Sanger Institute, Cambridge CB10 1SA, United Kingdom

²⁶ Department of Genetics, Genomics and Informatics, University of Tennessee Health Science Center, Memphis, TN 38163, USA

²⁷ Department of Ecology & Evolution and Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, University of Lausanne, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland